

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MARIN****FIRST NAME: DANINI****PROGRAM CODE: GHPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-13)
3. Literature Review (EUCLID 2019, 17-22)
4. Style Guide (EUCLID 2019, 24-26)
5. Chicago Manual of Style (EUCLID 2019, 44-55)
6. American Versus British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-34)
7. Latin Expressions and Abbreviations (EUCLID 2019, 56-59)

THE BASICS OF ESSAY WRITING: AN OVERVIEW

1) INTRODUCTION

The ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1 was inclusive of nine chapters dedicated to essay writing and its key elements. It started with the information on Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4). Essential components that will be utilized in the course were highlighted such as the Chicago Manual of Styles (EUCLID 2019, 44-55) which is the preferred style to be used while providing an overview of a style guide (EUCLID 2019, 24-26). It included tips on how to avoid plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-13) and how to conduct literature reviews (EUCLID 2019, 17-22). Additionally, it provided recommendations when writing papers (EUCLID 2019, 14-16), common Latin abbreviations and expression used in writing (EUCLID 2019, 56-59) and sample correction to papers (EUCLID 2019, 36-43). In this paper, seven chapters are discussed from a personal perspective.

2) REACTION TO THE STUDY MATERIAL

a) Essay Writing

An overview of key elements of essay writing were presented on the study material. It served as a review to what, over the years, has been taught at the various levels of academic studies and that are of essential importance in writing an essay. The basics of essay writing process should start early by defining the question, analyzing the tasks, developing an initial plan. Next, the topic of the essay should be researched and include activities such as reading material from other writers and researchers, making note of these so that after concluding this activity, ideas can be organized. Once this occurs, the essay drafting begins, and I should ensure that it has a structure that includes the Introduction, Body and Conclusion. Since the topic of the essay is researched, the essay must include references. When the essay is complete, one must proofread and be prepared to edit to improve prior to submission.

The essay writing review included in the coursepack reminded me of what I must look for when doing my routine essays. It was made as swift and clear to understand but when putting ideas into words, I have had challenges following the recommended order included in Chapter 1 (EUCLID 2019, 1). Knowing the elements of essay writing is essential for its adequate development aiming for a clear and understandable paper for our audience.

b) Plagiarism

Since essay writing involves researching the topic from material of other authors, one must give credit when necessary. Plagiarism should not take place as this would discredit the original author and I would be acting unethically as a professional. There are other ways in which the original author can be given credit when quoting, paraphrasing, using visuals and other data, for instance, through citation. I am able to utilize in-text citation and quotations. From the different types of quotations, I personally do not like to use long quotations and agree with the author that the use of quotations should be limited as this would dilute your unique piece of writing. On the other hand, paraphrasing is one of the options that I tend to use the most when including ideas, facts or other information shared by authors of researched papers. Although, I have used *signal phrases* to highlight statements by other authors in the past, the term was new to me. At the end of your paper, the bibliography includes the list of works that were cited, this way, I avoid plagiarism.

c) Literature Review

Like taking an English class, the Literature Review Chapter reviewed specific basics of linguistics. The chapter starts with eleven important reminders (EUCLID 2019, 17) of which the use of parallel construction to make a strong point and for the creation of a smooth flow caught my particular attention. Purdue Online Writing Lab (OWL) defines

this as “means using the same pattern of words to show that two or more ideas have the same level of importance.” After becoming aware of its meaning, I realized that it is a practice that I have while doing essay writing. I must say the last enlisted reminder which calls to omit unnecessary words (EUCLID 2019, 18) poses a challenge in my scientific writing and I should be keener when doing so. The subtitle What is the difference between “that” and “which”? had one statement on its content but I must say that it is one of the elements that at times puts me on pause when I pen my thoughts. When reading the subtitle Do I need a comma before the “and” (the conjunction) in a list of items? (EUCLID 2019, 20) I would consider the inclusion of the comma but habitually due to my personal choice I exclude it when writing a list of items. Similarly, using “and” to start a sentence is of limited use for me as indicated in this section of the chapter, only an experienced writer should attempt such feat (EUCLID 2019, 22). Clearly, some elements pointed out in this chapter call for more practice to advance in my writing skills and reminds me of what Ray Mancini once said, “The advanced level is mastery of the basics.”

d) Style Guide

A style guide is a means of documenting a writer’s approach to some elements of writing style that need to be consistent (EUCLID 2019, 24). This placed a question in my mind “Which style guide do I currently use?” As I figured, I tend to adhere to the standard English writing style but when writing scientific articles, I would review the style guide requested by the journal or organization. EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian) (EUCLID 2019, 24) as style guide. This has now challenged me to use the Turabian Style in my EUCLID papers.

e) Chicago Manual of Styles

Dr. Abel Scribe, PhD detailed the Chicago Manual of Styles (CMS) in Chapter 8 of the coursepack. He stated that the Chicago Style is the style of formatting books and research papers documented in the CMS, 2003, and Kate Turabian’s Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, 1996 (both published by the University of Chicago Press) (EUCLID 2019, 44). The CMS prefers the use of the Webster’s Third New International Dictionary (EUCLID 2019, 44) which is a well-known and recognized dictionary globally. Dr. Scribe’s chapter included guidance on Chicago Style and Usage for instance abbreviations, capitalizations, compound words, italics & quotation marks, numbers, quotations, page format, among others.

While learning the Chicago Style and Usage, I realized that it has laid out a set of guidelines that must be followed. My main challenge of which I had to patiently review was the page format and endnotes and footnotes. The reason for this is that the other elements outlined by Dr. Scribe are of seeming familiarity to the styles I have used while writing research papers. Keeping in mind that the paper of choice for CMS indicates white, 8 ½ by 11 inches with at least one inch margin, generally double-spacing is utilized and one-half inch indents (EUCLID 2019, 49-50), sets tone for a more formal presentation of my papers. As for the endnotes and footnotes, element that is cause of a blurred line in my

comprehension, I had to carefully review. The examples placed in this section were very helpful and I will certainly be using it as a guide when elaborating my papers. Since I must put the CMS into practice, this chapter gave a greater view of what was introduced in Chapter 5: What is a Style Guide, and Why Would I Need One?

f) American vs. British English Basic Differences and Influences of Change

Chapter 6 of the coursepack highlighted the differences of the use of American vs. British English. This chapter resounds the dilemma I encounter myself with daily. As a native of a former British Colony (Belize), English being our official language. The British English (linguistics) is taught in school. Despite of this, Belize is in Central America, with proximity to the United States of America. We rely heavily in Tourism and our main source is the American market. Due to this, I have seen a growing tendency in switching from British English and American English. Personally, I adapt myself to my audience, for example: if I am writing an official government correspondence, I do use British English but if it is a scientific article for an American organization, I would use American English. I do not find any difficulty in using either of them as I have grown in both environments.

The general categories of differences between American and British English were highlighted in this chapter. I can attest to the variation in pronunciation and spelling. The most challenging of both for me is the pronunciation. The material in the coursepack provides examples such as the different spelling, although same pronunciation (EUCLID 2019, 28) such as center vs. centre and color vs. colour (universally used words in our vocabularies). As for the Same Concept, Different Terms or Expressions: (or) Same Word, Difference in Style, Connotation and Frequency (EUCLID 2019, 30), I tend to categorize some of these as synonyms for example petrol – gasoline and good strain – freight train. I consider myself fortunate to experience at first hand the differences between these two variants of World English.

g) Latin Names and Expressions

I start by sharing one of my favorite Latin phrases that root from one of Paracelsus dictum, “dosis sola facit venenum” which means the dose makes the poison. During my formation as Pharmaceutical Chemist I had the opportunity to learn notable Latin phrases from scientists and philosophers. During scientific writing or reading, I come across such phrases. Chapter 9: Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (EUCLID 2019, 56) provided some of the most common that are used in writing. As common as the A.M. or P.M or as rare as ipso facto, these words are used by technical communicators (EUCLID 2019, 56). This chapter was succinct but provided a comprehensive list of Latin words or phrases that are recommended to be used in plain language.

3) CONCLUSION

The ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1 provided an overview of basic concepts needed to develop EUCLID assignments such as the response papers. While at first glance, it seemed like an overview of what I had learnt through the years in academic studies, I realized some elements I was taking for granted or am currently deficient of. Particularly, I became more knowledgeable in the Chicago Manual of Style. Following the How to Write a Response Paper (RP) (EUCLID 2019, 2-4) I found it challenging to apply what I had read in the coursepack. It is said that practice makes perfect and with the several papers that this course has on schedule, I aim to improve with the specific instructions using the material in this first segment of the course.

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